

NEW STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODEL FOR ASSESSING YOUTH ADULTS' RESILIENCE

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Abstract

Purpose – this research aims to analyze the resilient level of young adults using statistical techniques and propose a new structural model specific to the studied problem.

Methodology/approach - In order to measure the level of resiliency in participants, the authors used the CD-RISC questionnaire. It was completed by students. Current research statistically analyzes the proposed questionnaire for assessing the level of resilience (concept and dimensions), interprets the research tool, tests the statistical hypotheses suggested by the literature, presents a structural equation model (SEM) and analyzes results.

Findings – the research conducts a qualitative analysis of the concept of resilience, assessing resilience using a SEM and identification of the main indicators of resilience.

Research limitations/implications – the structural model of resilience is specific to the analyzed data obtained on the sample of respondents, but the methodology for obtaining this model is generally valid for quantitative analyzes based on the questionnaire.

Practical implications – The authors propose quantitative research for assessing the degree of resilience among young adults. Conclusions are issued, and solutions are proposed to reduce the negative effects of the COVID-19 period.

Originality/value – proposes the questionnaire, implements the research tools, tests the statistical hypotheses proposed by the literature, proposes the SEM.

Key words: Youth adults' resilience, Statistical analysis, Structural Equation Model.

Introduction

Researches indicate that resilience has many benefits (Hart, Wilson, & Hittner, 2006), is associated with a wide variety of risks and protective factors (Hemenover, 2003; McAdam-Crisp, 2006) and incites the interest of specialists (Smith & Carlson, 1997; White et al., 2008).

Resilience also needs to be approached complexly and specifically, as individuals can be resilient to certain aspects of life that others are not, manifesting themselves gradually (Hjemdal, 2007; Rutter, 2007). Adult resilience studies also involved populations that were perceived to be at risk, mainly due to illness or stressful experiences (Kobasa, 1979), but proved to be limited to generalization (Friborg, Barlaug, Martinussen, Roseninge and Hjemdal, 2005). Research on the resilience of adults (Reich, Zautra and Hall, 2010), has highlighted cases in which recovery occurs after an event with traumatic aspects, but also people in whom behavioural disorders have begun to develop against the background of traumatic events. Some authors Taylor (1983), who also mention the positive consequences of trauma, and Tedeschi and Calhoun (1995) identify several effects: the person appreciates each day more, develops beneficial relationships with family and friends, and changes their priorities.

The concept of resilience is a continuous dynamic determined by the following aspects:

1. Is resilience viewed from the perspective of the resistance, recovery, and transformation during life (Masten and O'Dougherty, 2010);

2. The contexts in which resilience is studied have become complex;
3. Resilience is seen not only as associated with trauma but from the perspective of situations of chronic adversity (poverty, accidents, unemployment, mental disorders).

In the last two years, researchers demonstrated the essential role of resilience during the COVID-19 pandemic (Chen & Bonanno, 2020; Prime et al., 2020). The individuals involved in social activities tend to be more resilient, although the mean score was lower than before the COVID-19 period. It was indicated that resilience buffers the negative association between the Big Five of neuroticism and COVID-19 stress (Zager Kocjan et al., 2021). Stability reduces stress and anxiety (Cazan & Truta, 2015) and may predict strategies used by people to react positively to stress. Highly resilient individuals tend to develop more adaptive coping strategies than maladaptive strategies (Denovan & Macaskill, 2017).

Organization of research

The authors of the study used statistical methods to identify the characteristics of young adults regarding their resilience in post COVID – 19 era.

The main objective of the research is the analysis of the level of resilience in young adults and the realization of a structure for this characteristic. To achieve this objective, the following theories are followed:

- The resilience characteristic at the population level underwent changes after the pandemic period, both from the point of view of the determining factors and at the level of the measured value.
- There is no difference in the resilience structure between the two groups of respondents (M/F)
- Building a structural model for the resilience characteristic adapted to the level of young adults

Material and method

The current research wants to operationalize the variable of psychological resilience on a group of students in the 1st and 2nd years of TUIASI after the pandemic period. The methodology includes the following steps:

1. Using a professional questionnaire to assess psychological resilience

In order to measure the level of trait resiliency in participants, the authors used the CD-RISC, the suggested self-report scale for measuring trait resiliency (Connor & Davidson, 2003). The CD-RISC contains 25 items with a 5-point range of responses as follows: not true at all (0), rarely true (1), sometimes true (2), often true (3), and true nearly all of the time (4). The total score ranges from 0 to 100, with higher scores reflecting greater resilience. Internal consistency, test-retest reliability, convergent and divergent validity of the scale is reported to be adequate and can easily distinguish between those with greater and lesser resilience (Connor & Davidson, 2003). The scale is structured as follows (5 dimensions):

- Dimension₁ (d1) - personal competence, high standards and tenacity, to which the items correspond: 10, 11, 12, 16, 17, 23, 24, 25;
- Dimension₂ (d2) - confidence in one's intuitions, tolerance to negative effects and invigorating effects of stress, with items: 6, 7, 14, 15, 18, 19, 20;
- Dimension₃ (d3) - positive acceptance of change and trusting relationships, to which the items correspond: 1, 2, 4, 5, 8;
- Dimension₄ (d4) - control, items: 13, 21, 22;
- Dimension₅ (d5) - spiritual influences, items: 3, 9.

2. Fixing the target group for assessing the level of psychological resilience.

The authors invited students enrolled in courses at Gheorghe Asachi Technical University of Iași, Romania, Economical Engineering specialization (n=123) to participate in an online questionnaire. Students who expressed interest were provided with a link to complete the questionnaire. The research using Google Forms was administered from May June 2022, during the post-COVID-19 pandemic

period. Informed consent was obtained virtually on the first page of the online questionnaire. Participation in the study was voluntary, and participants did not receive any compensation. However, the participants were informed regarding the questionnaire contents and the scale, and they were encouraged to use the feedback in case of misunderstands.

3. Refinement of the standard dimensions of the questionnaire on aspects that influence the level of resilience

All five dimensions are divided into the most critical aspects. Finally, the connection is made between the elements and the proposed items.

Table 1. Dimension 1: aspect-item coding

Encoding dimension_aspect_item	Aspect	Questionnaire item
d1_a1_item1	tenacity	10
d1_a1_item2	tenacity	12
d1_a1_item3	tenacity	16
d1_a1_item4	tenacity	24
d1_a2_item1	personal competence	11
d1_a2_item2	personal competence	23
d1_a3_item1	high standards	17
d1_a3_item2	high standards	25

Table 2. Dimension 2: aspect-item coding

Encoding dimension_aspect_item	Aspect	Questionnaire item
d2_a1_item1	positivity	6
d2_a1_item2	positivity	18
d2_a2_item1	trust in your own intuitions	7
d2_a2_item2	trust in your own intuitions	15
d2_a2_item3	trust in your own intuitions	20
d2_a3_item1	tolerance to negative effects	14
d2_a3_item2	tolerance to negative effects	19

Table 3. Dimension 3: aspect-item coding

Encoding dimension_aspect_item	Aspect	Questionnaire item
d3_a1_item1	acceptance of change	1
d3_a1_item2	acceptance of change	4
d3_a1_item3	acceptance of change	5
d3_a1_item4	acceptance of change	8
d3_a2_item1	trust in a relationship	2
d3_a2_item2	trust in a relationship	13

Table 4. Dimension 4: aspect-item coding

Encoding dimension_aspect_item	Aspect	Questionnaire item
d4_a1_item1	self-control	21
d4_a1_item2	self-control	22

Table 5. Dimension 5: aspect-item coding

Encoding dimension_aspect_item	Aspect	Questionnaire item
d5_a1_item1	faith	3
d5_a1_item2	faith	9

4. Validation of the measurement scale on each dimension separately and on the whole questionnaire.

Validation of the questionnaire on the data sets obtained will be done by analyzing the Cronbach's alpha coefficient, applied to each dimension separately and to the entire questionnaire. The analysis environment is SPSS 22. The value of the coefficient must be greater than 0,6 (for studies with a large number of respondents) (Taherdoost, 2020).

5. Checking the normality of each individual item

We applied the Shapiro-Wilk test to evaluate the normality of the value series. Applying the test to the series of items specifies that they are not normally distributed with a probability of 0,95. Because the analytically calculated p-value within the S-W test depends on the size of the series (the larger the size of the series of values, the lower the p-value, and for p-value <0,05, the hypothesis H0 is rejected: the series is normally distributed) the graphic check of normality was done (drawing Q-Q plot graphs for each item) and the z-score check for each individual series, the corroborated results support the fact that the series are not normally distributed and non-parametric tests will be applied for the subsequent statistical evaluation (Das, 2016).

Comparison of the level of resilience in the two groups of respondents (M/F) - to compare the structure of stability in young adults, the non-parametric Mann-Whitney U test for independent samples will be applied (Yonghwan Um, 2016).

Determination of a formative SEM (Structural Equation Model) for the analyzed study. The analysis environment is SmartPLS 3.0 (Kline, 2016).

The proposed conceptual model is a formative one (figure 1) that corresponds to the following relationship: $\sum_j^5 (b_j * \sum_{i=1}^n a_{ji} * aspect_i)$, where

$a_{ji, j=\overline{1..5}, i=\overline{1..n}}$ = loadings of the defined aspects that form Factors 1...5

$b_{j, j=\overline{1..5}}$ = the loadings of the factors for the formation of the construct for the assessment of resilience.

Fig.1 The formative Structural Equation Model

SEM represents a different modelling technique than the classical ones, which exclusively use a regression based on the method of least squares, linear modelling, logistic regression or other types of modelling. SEM represents a conceptual or natural structural environment, which supports the construction of models for different technical, economic, and psychological phenomena. This environment includes calculation theories, factorial analyses, causality analyses, statistical and least squares regressions, and econometric equations. The structural models created in this environment are dynamic, adaptable to the modelled phenomenon, complex, and multivariable, with the main characteristic of being able to correct measurement/observation errors. Another aspect of this structural model is that it systematically analyzes the respective causal models (cause-effect) and the relationships between the dependent and independent variables (it numerically quantifies the links between them). The third characteristic of SEM is the analysis of the indirect (mediation) effects generated by the independent or dependent variables on other variables within the causality systems.

Experimental results

Cronbach's Alpha coefficients for the entire questionnaire and the dimensions that group the 25 items are greater than 0,6, implying a high confidence level for the subsequent statistical analysis (table 6).

Table 6. Data validation

	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
All questionnaire	,907	25
Dimension1	,832	8
Dimension2	,689	7
Dimension3	,740	6
Dimension4	,658	2
Dimension5	,672	2

A new variable (resilience) was formed as the sum of the values of the 25 items. The normality of the newly formed series is analyzed. The three normality tests are the SW test (table 7), the graphical Q-Q method (figure 2), and the z-score for skewness and kurtosis (table 8) (Barato, 2015).

Table 7. The S-W test for the distribution of the resilience variable

Shapiro-Wilk test			
Statistic	df	Sig.	
,974	123	,018	

According to the SW test, the series is not normally distributed, being at the limit of the analytical value (Hanusz, 2015).

Table 8. The resilience variable – a descriptive statistic

Descriptive statistical parameters of resilience	Statistic	Std. Error	Z score
Mean	67,2195	1,18897	
Median	67,0000		
Variance	173,878		
Std. Deviation	13,18627		
Minimum	28,00		
Maximum	94,00		
Range	66,00		
Skewness	-,401	,218	-1,83
Kurtosis	,520	,433	1,2

The Z score belongs to the range [-1,96 ; 1,96]; thus, the resilience variable can be considered normally distributed (Greggory, 2017).

Fig. 2 Q-Q plot for resilience variable

Fig.3 The histogram of the resilience variable

We can consider that the resilience variable is approximately normally distributed.

Observing the resilience histogram for the entire group of respondents (figure 3), we can deduce that the structure of the resilience parameter was not significantly influenced by the Covid-19 pandemic. This can be explained by the fact that the respondents are at the lower limit of maturity, thus being protected within their families.

Another characteristic that shows us the normality of the level of resilience of the respondents is the average value (67.22), close to the lower limit of the interval in which it is considered that the level of resilience is high (70).

The first analyzed hypothesis - if there are differences in resilience between the two groups of respondents (M/F), it results in the fact that the two groups have a structure of the level of resilience approximately the same (figure 4).

Fig.4 The resilience variable structure (M/F)

The only two differences are d2_a1_item1 – “I can make unpopular or difficult decisions that affect other people, if necessary”, group1 (M) having a mean rank of 72.29 compared to group 2, mean rank = 55.79 (figure 5) and d4_a1_item1 – “When there are no clear solutions for my problems, sometimes fate or God can help me” - the average rank in group 1 is 53.47 compared to 67.28 in group 2 (figure 6).

Fig.5 The first different aspect d2_a1_item1

Fig.6 The second different aspect d4_a1_item1

The proposed model for resilience (SEM), programmed in the SmartPLS 3.0 environment, is presented in figure 7.

Fig.7 The SEM for youth adults' resilience

It is observed that the most important dimensions that form the resilience construct are dimension d3, with the two aspects "acceptance of change" and "trust in a relationship", with a loading coefficient of 0,627 and dimension d1, with the three aspects (tenacity, personal competence, high standards) with a loading coefficient of 0,43.

Another observation that derives from the built model is the dimension d5 (Faith) that enters the resilience construct with a weighting coefficient of -0,005, which leads to the conclusion that an increased level of faith does not influence the level of resilience in young adults at all.

Even the increased level of the self-control variable (d4) is not seen as a positive factor for the level of resilience (figure 8).

Fig. 8 SEM coefficients

Discussions and conclusions

The proposed model for measuring the level of resilience depends on the moment of application of the questionnaire to the group of respondents, external factors, and the structure of the group of respondents (age, qualification, responsibilities).

The analysis methodology can be applied redundantly to the same group of respondents or another, and the results can be compared.

The paper proposes a statistical methodology for an extremely variable, dynamic, difficult to quantify psychological parameter (resilience level) and implements a structural model based on latent variables.

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